

METHODOLOGY OF WORKING ON THE CLASS OF NOUNS IN PRIMARY CLASSES

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Abstract: this article contains ideas and methods for working on nouns in primary grades. The methods cover four classes.

Key words: independent vocabulary, lexical group, practical knowledge, possession, agreement, person, method, comparison, grammatical signs.

The linguistic basis of the methodology of working on word groups is the science of word groups, the division of words into groups based on lexical, grammatical and syntactic features. Vocabulary teaching in primary grades relies mainly on practical knowledge. This class program does not intend to provide students with in-depth information about word groups, but the teacher practically introduces children to the signs that represent the general state of word groups, that is, their distinguishing features. The main goal of teaching vocabulary to a child is to develop students' oral and written speech, to enrich their vocabulary with new words, to achieve a clear understanding of the meaning of words that have been used so far, to connect formation of skills of appropriate use of this or that word in speech is considered. In order to effectively implement this goal, in the process of studying word groups, words with similar and opposite meanings, their literal or figurative use, are introduced. In imparting this knowledge, it is important to

connect it with the personal experiences of the students and what they have seen directly.

During the preparatory period for teaching the horse, students should pay attention to the objects and the meaning of the words that are their names. In order to divide words into groups based on their lexical meaning, to form an understanding of all their features, students need to learn the meaning of the word as well as master the grammatical signs. After the preparation stage in teaching the noun, the lexical meanings and grammatical signs of the noun, i.e., what kind of question is the answer, what it expresses, distinguishing nouns depending on the question and connect them with the noun knowledge and skills such as some spelling rules (for example, capitalizing nouns) are formed [1]. The stage of learning the horse deepens in each class. In the second grade, practical knowledge is given about the lexical meaning of nouns, common nouns and common nouns. The system of studying nouns is a goal-oriented process, in which the generalized meaning and grammatical features of this word group are studied in a clear sequence in a scientifically based relationship with each other, as well as related to the noun group. the exercises performed in order to form the skills of correct use of words in speech and correct writing are gradually becoming more complicated. In the educational program, the characteristics of the noun as a language phenomenon, the tasks of learning it, the size of the material for each class and the consistency of their learning are determined in accordance with the age characteristics of the students. There are a number of tasks for teaching nouns in primary grades. They are the following [2]

1. Formation of general information and practical knowledge about nouns;
2. Differentiate them from each other and divide them into groups by asking questions;
3. Formation of spelling rules for famous nouns;
4. Introduction to the number of nouns, i.e. singular and plural forms;

5. Formation of skills of correct use of possessive adjectives;
6. Forming general skills about contracts;
7. To increase vocabulary, to be able to use nouns correctly in speech;
8. Analysis of words, comparison.

The above-mentioned tasks are not given detailed information separately, but are solved in relation to each other. But at the same time, more importance is given to solving a task that must be performed at a certain stage of learning a horse.

For example, in the first and second grades, the signs of nouns are studied as a group of words mentioned above, while in the third grade, emphasis is placed on imparting knowledge about the use of nouns in the singular and plural. At the last stage of the primary class, attention is paid to learning the use of possessive adverbs and agreements. The task of developing the speech and thinking of primary school students is solved at each stage of teaching the subject. The number of nouns, that is, their use in the singular and plural, is made on the basis of comparison. For example, it is possible to prove an idea on the basis of the words bread-bread, flower-flower. Based on the conversation, it is said that bread represents one object, and bread represents two or more objects, and a simple conclusion can be drawn from it. If one object is represented, singular, if two or more objects are represented, nouns are plural. But it is a bit difficult to give practical knowledge about possessive suffixes. After all, elementary school students do not have the concept of personality. Observations show that in forming an understanding of possessive adverbs, based on the lexical meaning of the word "Ownership" (ownership means ownership) it will be effective to create skills. As an independent set of words, a noun is distinguished by having specific lexical meanings and specific grammatical signs. Meanings and grammatical signs of nouns are somewhat complicated, therefore, students' knowledge of nouns is gradually formed in the process of performing practical tasks. Therefore, the main focus is on providing more practical knowledge about horses in the primary classes in order to create general

understanding, knowledge, skills and abilities. Innovative methods are effective in strengthening this knowledge. These methods should be suitable for the age characteristics of students, their strength and capabilities. The success of any method depends on the teacher's ability to use it in appropriate situations and with what questions he applies it. Using the cognitive activity of a young student with the questions encountered along the way does not give the expected effect and result.[3] The expected results of the methods will depend on the orientation of the teacher's questions to the important aspects of the grammatical event, the situation, the characteristics of the topic being explained, and the teaching tools and weapons. That is, the methods are chosen based on the possibility. Pupils perform the tasks given by the teacher orally or in writing depending on his characteristics. Practical knowledge is more important than theoretical knowledge when teaching nouns in elementary grades. The above points show that the role of modern methods in creating sufficient knowledge about horses based on the standards set in primary classes is extremely large. We began to use a number of methods in the process of scientifically working on this topic, and I think that it will have the expected effect in the course of the primary school students. "Five Fingers", "Fan", "Pillapoya", "Charkhpalak" and "Energizers" that give energy to the student are effective in teaching the vocabulary. Observations show that the above methods are compatible with the requirements (the characteristics of the subject and the strength and abilities of students). "Five fingers" method can be used to teach all word groups. Working with small groups is effective for elementary school students. Together with providing practical knowledge, this method helps to activate young students. A set of common signs and characteristics of this word group helps students to form a solid understanding of the noun group. The "Five Fingers" method summarizes this total. When using this method, one characteristic of the horse will be reflected in each finger. That is:

1. What meaningful words are considered to be nouns;

2. Noun questions;
3. Words that answer the question of who;
4. Words that answer the question of what;
5. Words that answer the question of where.

It can be seen from the above that consistency and connection are important in learning word groups. Based on the characteristics of this method, its use in first graders gives the expected result. "Energizers" can be used in all elementary classes, except for the first classes, which can give quickness and energy in the process of teaching young students. Another interactive method used in elementary school mother tongue and reading literacy classes is the "Cluster" method. The word cluster means connection. Clusters can be used in the stages of the lesson, awareness and thoughts. This method is like a structure that allows you to think about the connections between different ideas. "Cluster" method can be used to work with students individually or in groups. This method makes it possible to generalize the studied topic and find connections between them. In "Cluster", words, phrases, and sentences are written on the class board or sheet of paper. For example, students' interest in the lesson increases when the branching method is used to learn vocabulary. The branching method can be used to form the concept of "Nouns" in the third grade. In this case, the teacher addresses the students with the following questions.

- What groups did we divide the words according to the meaning of subject and place?

Their answer is written on the board.

- What name can we call people, things and places together?

Using nouns in topic clustering before learning the topic encourages students to think in new ways. According to Methodist scientists, clustering proves to be a "Knowledge Access Strategy" in the process of starting to learn a topic.

Summary: In our country, the changes in the social sphere and the increase of intellectual potential will motivate the acquisition of modern knowledge. Innovative changes in the field of education and bringing them to a level that meets the new advanced requirements of our time is one of the important tasks and goals. The textbooks, which are being changed in harmony with the foreign education system, are aimed at developing thinking, creative abilities, and expanding imagination, so they require practical knowledge in forming every concept of linguistics in the student. Methods are the basis of imparting practical knowledge.

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